

SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT AWARENESS AND PRACTICES AMONG JUNIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the solid waste management awareness and practices among junior high school students, using non-experimental quantitative research design specifically, the descriptive and comparative research designs, utilizing adopted structure survey questionnaire about Awareness of Students on Waste Management and Practices on Solid Waste Management. Participants of this study were selected using stratified random sampling. Findings of this study revealed that junior high schools exhibit a commendable awareness about solid waste management (mean=4.36). The results also revealed that in terms of segregation and reduce practices students demonstrate excellent performance (mean=3.09), (mean=3.25), respectively. The results showed that there is a highly significant difference among the awareness and practices of junior high school students.

Keywords – *solid waste management awareness, solid waste management practices, descriptive research design, comparative research designs*

INTRODUCTION

Context and Rationale

Globally, poor solid waste management is a major contributor to both plastic pollution, which harms the marine environment and is projected to cost \$13 billion

annually, and climate change, which accounts for 5% of worldwide carbon emissions. Inadequate Municipal Solid Waste Management (MSWM) systems are the source of about 80% of plastic found in the ocean. According to Bundhoo (2018), growing amounts of solid waste are a global concern, with least developed countries (LDCs) being disproportionately impacted by inadequate waste management systems. This exponential growth in the generation of solid waste is even more concerning. In the most impoverished nations, it is predicted to triple by 2050 and to double in large and medium-sized cities. With the lack of sanitary landfills, recycling centers, and incinerators in low-income nations, this is particularly concerning. As such, the majority of their garbage is disposed of in open dumps, badly managed, and without treatment (Vergara and Jammi 2023).

Solid waste management practices have always been a major concern in the community on a daily basis. It is seemingly impossible to implement the practices and consciousness in regard to having no commitment and support from the local authorities. It should start from the foundation of education to further implement such practices and consciousness in regard to having no commitment and support from the local authorities. It should start from the foundation of education to further implement such practices and, students are the one who shapes the current generations and generations to come. This study focused on assessing how the junior high school students perceive the essence of solid waste management and practices and how they practically help the community. The students are commonly subjected to the production of waste management, in some other aspect of being uneducated in realizing the effects of it. As stated by Molina and Catan (2021), many of them have not enough knowledge regarding the effects of improper waste disposal, solid waste prohibited activities and even school initiatives toward the practices of a clean and safe environment.

According to the World Bank (2024), the globe annually produces 2.01 billion tonnes of municipal solid garbage, of which, at the very least, 33 percent are not managed in a way that is safe for the environment. The amount of waste produced daily per person in the world varies greatly, ranging from 0.11 to 4.54 kg on average. High-income nations produce almost 34%, or 683 million tonnes, of the world's trash, but making up only 16% of the global population. Overall, waste production and income level are positively correlated. Compared to low- and middle-income countries, where it is anticipated to increase by at least 40%, high-income countries are predicted to see a 19% increase in daily per capita trash creation by 2050. When income levels rise, waste creation rises more quickly at low income levels than it does at high income levels after first declining at the lowest income levels. By 2050, it is anticipated that the overall amount of garbage produced in low-income nations will have increased by more than three times.

As such, the process of managing waste has been a huge control of humans in light of a day-to-day cleaning drive. It is a humanitarian concern in which should focus our minds and attention to prevent the disease it can bring to the general public. If it can't practice the proper ways of disposing of products, it can lead to a socio-economic problem that needs to be recalibrated and changed. According to Ike et al. (2018), solid waste is an environmental concern and challenge of today's generation. Solid waste

management sometimes ascribed from poor collection of waste and disposal methods and lack of dangers in poor sanitary areas. Furthermore, if we can no longer contain the waste disposing every day, we will fail to plan the waste management system and can nearly affect the public health of the people. Solid waste is a serious problem that world is facing on a daily basis. It is a constant improper practice of humans, disposing of their trash in a winding way. Yet, it is one of the most pressing issues that needs to be changed.

Partly, the collaboration within the people in the community broadens the scope of awareness and practices which can improve the habit and attitude of people toward solid waste. It is something that concerns the community, on how they navigate the importance of waste management, in making unwanted waste to be more convertible and equitable towards a healthier environment (Schiavo, 2021).

This carries the objective of identifying students' awareness and practices on waste management. Along with this, the research determines the level of awareness about waste management in terms of regulations, standards, and health and environmental effects. Additionally, this determines the level of solid waste management practices of students in terms of segregation and reduction. Furthermore, this will compare the level of awareness and practices about waste management among junior high school students. Lastly, it will develop a program that will contribute to students' awareness and practices in waste management.

As specified by Akintunde (2017) with increased knowledge, individuals tend to make environmentally friendly decisions and take responsible steps towards achieving a sustainable environment. Thus, the people in the society will live in a healthy and pollution free environment.

Review of Related Literature and Studies

One of the main duties of municipal administrators and a useful stand-in for good governance is solid waste management, or SWM. Sustainable urban management (SWM) reduces negative effects on the environment and public health, preserves resources, and makes cities more livable. SWM practices that are not sustainable, however, have a detrimental effect on environmental sustainability and public health. This problem is further worsened by fast urbanization as well as institutional and budgetary constraints (Abubakar et al, 2022).

According to Muljaningsih and Galuh (2018), waste is an inevitable by-product of human activities. Nature of waste is determined by the material being consumed by the people and waste management is linked to human lifestyle. Absence of proper waste management is one of the pressing environmental issues that is directly influenced by modern lifestyle (Kumar & Kumar, 2020).

As specified by Asteria and Haryanto (2021), integrated waste management highlights the 3R rule consisting of reduce, reuse, and recycle followed by incineration

and final disposal which is ideally conducted where waste material originates. Subsequently, 3R faced challenges when society had limited awareness regarding classifying and segregating waste. (Muljaningsih & Galuh, 2018). Lack of awareness and practices can hinder effective waste management.

In the study of Pujara et al. (2019), a popular approach for disposing of MSW in most Indian cities, except metro areas, is open dumping. Due to the direct burning and/or degradation of wastes, this method emits harmful and greenhouse gases (GHGs), which pose serious dangers to the environment and human health. Consequently, there is a great demand for integrated solid waste management (ISWM), which uses a variety of techniques including incineration, composting, anaerobic digestion, refuse-derived fuel, material recovery facilities, and sanitary landfilling. As stated by Debrah et al. (2021), the issue of solid waste management (SWM) is complex and involves elements of politics, socioeconomics, institutions, and the environment. Metropolitan spaces in emerging countries are facing a major difficulty due to exponential increase in metropolitan areas. The disparity in environmental awareness between young and old people in developing nations causes problems with waste management or ecology, which leads to unsustainable development and has serious repercussions in low-income countries. As stated by Bautista (2019), many environmental issues facing the planet must be addressed on a personal level, necessitating the development of awareness among people that will lead them to adopt ecologically friendly behaviors.

Conceptual Framework

This study was used Input-Process-Output Model. The focus of this research was to determine the students' level of awareness and practices on solid waste management.

For input, it is about waste management awareness and solid waste management practices. Waste management awareness has three indicators which are awareness on regulations, awareness on standards, and awareness on health environmental effects. On the other hand, solid waste management practices has two indicators which are segregation and reduce.

For process, descriptive analysis was used to describe the level of waste

management awareness of students and comparative analysis was used to compare the level of solid waste management practices among junior high school students.

For output, the research proposed a program named Waste Wise: Promoting Sustainable Practices in Solid Waste Management.

Research Questions

The purpose of this study is to know the level of solid waste awareness and practices among junior high school students.

Specifically, this study answer the following questions:

1. How may the solid waste management awareness of junior high school students be described in terms of:
 - 1.1 Awareness on regulations;
 - 1.2 Awareness on standards; and
 - 1.3 Awareness on health environmental effects?
2. How may the solid waste management practices of junior high school students be described in terms of:
 - 2.1 Segregation; and
 - 2.2 Reduce?
3. Are there significant differences in solid waste management awareness and practices among the different grade levels of junior high school?
4. What program on solid waste management awareness and practices can be developed based on the results of the study?

Hypothesis

This study was guided and tested the hypothesis below:

There are no significant differences in solid waste management awareness and practices among the different grade levels of junior high school.

Significance of the Study

This study was essential and important in the field of science education. It shows the level of awareness and practices among junior high school students on the importance of solid waste management. As for students, the strategy to conduct activities in the study may help the students in providing them an opportunity and chance to dig deeper about one's eco- consciousness in the impact of solid waste management on the student's level of awareness. Next is the teachers, the result of the study served as a guide to implement programs and practices to help reduce wastes in proper way of disposal. Thus, extend the knowledge on solid waste management practices to further disseminate the information in public to provide feasible activities on solid waste problems. As for the school administrators, the study's conclusions helped administrators run their own institutions and provided a platform for motivating educators to adapt different programs and practices to instill the importance of solid waste management in the general public.

The Department of Education (DepEd) will serve as a bridge to improve the existing curriculum that will disseminate information about solid waste management to develop public awareness of the solid waste problem with the integration of environmental awareness and knowledge in their curricula. Lastly, the future researchers feel that this study's findings assisted later researchers in performing a similar study with additional factors or in-depth investigation. In addition, the researchers will implement programs to instill the awareness of having good solid waste management and further develop strategies and programs to help ensure the continuing education and information on solid waste management.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research utilized the non-experimental quantitative research design using descriptive and comparative research designs to develop and propose a program on solid waste management and practices. Descriptive evaluation quantitative research design is an approach that provides a detailed description about the experiences or perspective of respondents. Descriptive comparative quantitative research design is an approach that involves comparing the behavior of different groups. Descriptive evaluation quantitative research design was used to describe the level of students' solid waste management awareness and practices. Additionally, descriptive comparative quantitative research design was employed to compare the solid waste management awareness and practices among the different grade levels of junior high school.

Respondents and Sampling

A total of 112 junior high school students participated in the study, of which 26 are Grade 7 students, 29 are Grade 8 students, 28 are Grade 9 students and 29 are Grade 10 students. They were chosen because they are capable of providing information that is being asked in the study. Informed consent was used in accordance with ethical guidelines. Informed permission forms were given to the participants, who were asked to indicate to them whether or not they were willing to participate in the study.

Furthermore, a stratified random sampling method was used to randomly select the students per level of junior high school students. Thus, the probability of selecting a cluster is commensurate with its size.

Instrumentation

Awareness of Students on Waste Management. Data on students' level of awareness in waste management was collected using a structured questionnaire adapted from a research study entitled Student's Awareness on Waste Management: Their Effect on Waste Management Practices by Annaliza Panganiban-Santos, MaEd and Ray Rudolf Pastrana (2021). The questionnaire is composed of three indicators

such as awareness on regulations, awareness on standards, and awareness on health and environment effects. Awareness on regulations have three statements. Awareness on standards composed of six statements. Awareness on health and environment effects have two statements.

The survey questionnaire entitled Awareness of Students on Waste Management was composed of five indicators and rating scale these are very great extent (5), great extent (4), moderate extent (3), least extent (2), and none at all (1).

Practices on Solid Waste Management. Data on students' level of waste management practices was collected using a structured questionnaire adapted from the research study entitled Level of Awareness and Practices on Solid Waste Management among Students in Iligan National High School, Iligan City by Cahoy (2013). The questionnaire is composed of two indicators which are segregation and reduce. Practices on solid waste management in terms of segregation and reduce have five statements each.

The survey questionnaire entitled Practices on solid waste management in terms of segregation and reduce was composed of four indicators and rating scale these are always (4), often (3), seldom (2), and never (1).

Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers prepared all the necessary documents such as letter of approval and survey questionnaire. After getting permission, the researchers met with the students, gave them the assent and consent form, and explained to them why the study was being conducted. They were also informed that the answers they provided on the questionnaire would be kept completely confidential and used only for that purpose. First, the researchers gave the letter of approval to the school of the participants asking for the permission to conduct the study. Next, the survey questionnaires were distributed and momentarily answered by the students. Last, the collection of survey questionnaires. After the student answered the questions, the researchers explained the nature of the checklist in view of the awareness and practices on solid waste management. The assessment took only 60 minutes.

Data Analysis

After collecting all the questionnaires, data were organized, tallied, tabulated and analyzed using some statistical tools. Descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation were used to describe the students' level of awareness and practices in solid waste management. One-Way Anova was performed to compare solid waste management awareness and practices among the different grade levels of junior high school.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this study, 112 respondents from junior high school were included in descriptive statistics and one-way anova analyses. The results aimed to assess and compare the level of solid waste management awareness and practices among junior high school students. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze the awareness and practices of students on waste management. One-way anova was used to test if there is a significant differences in solid waste management awareness and practices among the different grade levels of junior high school.

Table 1.
Awareness of Students on Waste Management

Awareness of Students on Waste Management	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Awareness on Rules	3.77	Great Extent
Awareness on Standards	4.50	Very Great Extent
Awareness on Health and Environment Effects	4.81	Very Great Extent
Overall	4.36	Great Extent

Legend:

4.50-5.00 Very Great Extent

3.50-4.49 Great Extent

2.50-3.49 Moderate Extent

1.50-2.49 Least Extent

1.00-1.49 None at all

The data in Table 1 shows the mean and verbal interpretation on the Awareness of Students on Waste Management in terms of regulations, standards, and health and environmental effects was great extent as shown by the overall mean value of 4.36. Among the three indicators students poses high level of awareness on health and environmental effects as shown in the table (mean=4.81). On the other hand, they demonstrate great extent of awareness on rules (mean=3.77).

The results implies that the junior high school students possess satisfactory level of awareness about solid waste management. The findings of this study support the studies conducted by Paghastian (2017), according to their study the students have enough knowledge about solid waste management. It is also parallel to the study of Panganiban-Santos and Pastrana (2021), revealed that junior high school and senior high school students have very great extent awareness in terms of solid waste management.

Table 2.
Practices on Solid Waste Management in Terms of Segregation and Reduce

Practices of Students on Waste Management	Mean	Verbal Interpretation
Segregation	3.09	Good

Reduce	3.25	Very Good
Overall	3.17	Good

Legend:

3.25-4.00 Very Good

2.50-3.24 Good

1.75-2.49 Fair

1.00-1.74 Poor

The Table 2 shows the practices on solid waste management in terms of segregation and reduce among the junior high school students. The total mean score response of segregation got 3.09 with a verbal interpretation of 'Good' in which revealed that students perform so well in segregating mixed-waste processes suggesting that these students really segregate the waste properly, because the students classify the waste properly and at the same time, they keep separate containers of trash based on its physical properties and students oftentimes segregate non-harmful waste from toxic waste to prevent failing to segregate trade waste that ends up mixed in the bins. On the other hand, the mean score interpretation regarding the practices on solid waste management in terms of reduce among the junior high school students got the overall total mean interpretation response of 3.25 with a verbal description of "Very Good" suggesting that the students still practiced the reduction of materials on solid waste management. Implying that most students practiced reducing waste materials in order to not contribute in building up waste products and still indicates that the students had a good practice for waste reduction through bringing reusable water bottles than buying water in one-used.

Overall, the overall total mean interpretation got 3.17 with a verbal description of 'Good' suggesting that students maintain a clean environment and support the prevention of contamination. These outcomes suggest that most of the students segregating and reducing their waste into respective containers and classify the waste based on its type. Segregation of waste is still being practiced to recycle and help treat waste directly. In line in supporting the waste segregation process, the study findings of Verma and Borongan (2022) suggests that the existing solid waste collection routes require route optimization. We have determined the distance between the central garbage collection office and the bin using the shortest path routing method, ensuring that the collection vehicle visits more bins along the route. In order to maximize fuel efficiency and provide affordable collection management, the collection route is optimized. In result of this, waste management in the city is made easier by employing this technique.

Moreover, this also implies that the students are more environmentally aware to reduce their usage of materials in all aspects of living. As stated by Dahlawi and Sharkawy (2021) that a good program for the practical use of this rubbish, starting with sorting and recycling, reduces the quantity of waste that ends up in landfills, preserves resources, and promotes recyclable materials. In result, waste combinations that aren't necessary can be seen and can help with appropriate segregation techniques.

Table 3.

One –way Analysis between Awareness and Practices of Students on Waste Management

Groups	F	P	Interpretation	Decision
Awareness	20.13	0.001	Highly Significant	Reject the HO
Practices	3.08	0.034	Highly Significant	Reject the HO

The table 3 shows the result of one –way analysis of variance among the awareness and practices of students on waste management. The results show that students' awareness sig. one-way (0.001) is less than alpha value of (0.01). This means that the null hypothesis is rejected which signifies that there is a highly significant difference among the awareness of junior high school students. However, students' practices in solid waste management has a p-value of (0.034) which is less than the alpha value of (0.01). This means that the null hypothesis is rejected which signifies that there is a highly significant difference among the practices of junior high school students.

The results of the study regarding the solid waste management practices, attitudes, and awareness of university staff and students are closely related, which implies that education is a strategic way to successfully implementing a solid waste management program. In order to ensure that the goals for the well-being of people and the environment are realized, schools have a significant role to play in raising people's awareness of the implications of their activities. More precisely, through good environmental education, academic community members develop positive attitudes, become more worried about the growing problem of solid waste, and are motivated to work together to mitigate the issue (Madrigal and Oracion, 2018). Results of this study was parallel to the study of Molina and Catan (2021), revealed that senior high school students in Zamboanga City, Philippines demonstrate good solid waste management in terms of segregation and reduce.

Table 4.

Waste Wise: Promoting Sustainable Practices in Solid Waste Management

Component	Objective	Strategy	Person Responsible	Budget
Education and Awareness	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Increase awareness about sustainable waste management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conduct school seminars Distribute brochures Integration of solid waste 	Teacher and School Administrator	Php 1000.00

	practices among junior high school students.	management in school curriculum		
Implementation of Sustainable Practices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote recycling projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide recycling bins Create recycling organization and sell it 	School Administrator, Utility Worker, and School Club Officers	Php 1000.00
Community Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Engage the community in eco-friendly activities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Organize a clean-up drives activities Encourage students to create a youth-led organization 	Community Officer, Community, and School Administrator	Php 500.00
Monitoring and Evaluation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Assess the state of solid waste in the community 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conduct a monitoring activities thrice a week Conduct a research on how to solve solid waste management challenges 	Monitoring Team and Researcher	Php 2000.00

The results of the study may be an important baseline in improving and expanding the existing solid waste management awareness and practices programs and initiating new programs to reduce system waste scantines. These initiatives will enable the nearby communities and schools to encourage them how to manage the garbage and actively divert waste to promote waste reduction.

Conclusions

The solid waste management methods and awareness among junior high school students are presented in this study. The findings showed that students understand the meaning of solid waste, the consequences of improper disposal, activities that are prohibited when it comes to solid waste, school initiatives related to solid waste, the significance of solid waste management, and students' duties. Students, however, know very little about the several rules that are pertinent to solid waste management. These results imply that extensive informational campaigns about rules pertaining to solid waste management should be carried out by educational institutions and other interested parties. The following factors can be blamed for the amount of solid waste management awareness: friends, peers and school. This research implies that the government can use

these channels to spread knowledge about intensively solid waste management. In terms of segregation, reduction, reuse, recycling, and disposal, the results also showed that students follow good solid waste management procedures in having environmental awareness on a day-to-day basis. The researchers proposed a program named Waste Wise: Promoting Sustainable Practices in Solid Waste Management.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, several recommendations are proposed such as encouraging students to participate in recycling programs, incorporating educational programs about solid waste management awareness and practices into school curriculum at all levels to possess environmentally behaviour at an early age, developing solid waste management policies for school to maintain the cleanliness of school. Furthermore, future researchers may utilized this a basis for their research study about solid waste management awareness and practices.

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Compliance with Ethical Considerations

To adhere to ethical considerations in conducting this research, all participants were required to read and sign a consent form indicating their voluntary agreement to participate in this study. To safeguard participants' confidentiality, names, addresses, and other personal details were not included in the study. Data collected from the volunteered participants were stored only in the temporary folder on the researchers' laptop. Access to the data was strictly limited to the researchers themselves to ensure security. All the data were handled with utmost care such that only the researchers were able to analyse them to avoid the unauthorized transfer or access of data. After finalizing the paper, the researchers waited until the full completion of the study, after which the researcher deleted all files in the personal laptop and the researchers did not keep any copy of the respondents' data.

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